

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Media Based on Technology to Study Spoken Javanese Politeness

To cite this article: Y Widiyono *et al* 2020 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **1573** 012001

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

IOP | ebooks™

Bringing together innovative digital publishing with leading authors from the global scientific community.

Start exploring the collection—download the first chapter of every title for free.

Media Based on Technology to Study Spoken Javanese Politeness

Y Widiyono^{1*}, Rochimansyah¹, A Aryanto¹, H Setyowati¹ and K Saddhono²

¹ Universitas Muhammadiyah Purworejo, Indonesia

² Universitas Sebelas Maret Surakarta, Indonesia

*widiyono@umpwr.ac.id

Abstract. Being able to speak using *unggah-ungguh basa* (speech levels) is one of the indicators of students' speaking skill in Javanese language. The use of IT-based teaching media can be an alternative way to develop students' speaking skill and stimulate students' creativity, innovation, and thinking skills as well. This was a quasi experiment carried out at Senior High School in Purworejo, Central Java, Indonesia. The finding was the average score of the control group was 74.5 and that of the experimental group was 82.2. T-test showed that t_{table} was 4.87 and t_{count} was 2.000. The research confirms that IT-based teaching media are effective to teach Javanese speaking skill using *unggah-ungguh basa* (speech levels).

Keywords: Media, Technology, spoken, Javanese Politeness

1. Introduction

Information and technology (IT) advancement plays a great role in education domain nowadays. IT is rapidly changing and it offers innovation in the teaching-learning process. Rahman and Ma stated that the use of IT is expected to give information services and help students learn independently [1]. Each lesson has its own characteristics to reach learning objectives. So does Javanese lesson particularly in teaching *unggah-ungguh basa* (speech levels). The role of audio-visual media is crucial to enable students in observing, identifying and comprehending the concepts of *unggah-ungguh basa*.

Regional languages have strategic position. They are national heritage that play a great role to preserve local wisdom and to shape students' character. As stated in European Charter, regional languages are languages traditionally spoken in a particular area by people who are statistically smaller than other populations within a country. Former director of UNESCO, Sheldon Shaeffer (2004), in an international seminar hosted by SEAMEO QITEP in Language in Jakarta under the theme *The Use of Regional Language/Mother Tongue to Improve Elementary School Students' Competence* stated that preserving regional languages is urgent. Among 6.000 languages in the world, as many as 40% are endangered. Only 10% can survive. Suwondo [2] stated that according to UNESCO report, 3.000 out of 6.000 languages around the globe are almost extinct; most of them are owned by minority ethnics.

Similar statement was given by Suwondo [3] who argued that in Indonesia there are around 726 regional languages, but only 456 which have been identified. Endangered languages are mainly from

outside Java island. In his statement, there are 400 identified regional languages in Indonesia. There are 13 languages with more than a million native speakers. One of them is Javanese. Javanese has a strategic position with a great number of native speakers. A survey by Ethnologue showed that the language was in rank 12 with 75.5 million of native speakers [4]. It is a means of communication for people living in Java island, other islands across Indonesia, as well as Suriname [5].

Javanese has several *unggah-ungguh basa* (speech levels). Harjawiyan [6] pointed out that they are generally simplified into two: *krama* and *ngoko*. *Krama* (high speech level) is used to speak to older people or strangers. Meanwhile, *ngoko* (low speech level) is used to speak to peers or younger friends. The *unggah-ungguh basa* point out distance, respect, and familiarity [7]. Unfortunately, the intensity of speaking using *unggah-ungguh basa* is decreasing among Javanese people. This especially happens to youth [8]. Sasangka [9] stated that *unggah-ungguh basa* teaches politeness values in speaking and behaving. In addition, respect and harmony are two vital things in communication among Javanese people [10]. Based on classroom observation, students' interest and motivation to learn Javanese was still low. Students found it difficult to master *unggah-ungguh basa*. This resulted in unsatisfactory learning outcomes. Thus, the use of teaching media is necessarily needed.

The teaching media as tools to create, store, and present instructional content [11][12]. Media are vital to promote academic performance [13]. Rao [14] argued that they can also become a facilitator in the teaching-learning process. Naz and Akbar [15] added that teaching media can engage students in the learning process.

There are two kinds of teaching media namely technical and non-technical [16]. Technical media are technological innovations in language teaching which involve the use of mechanical paraphernalia. The instances are video players, Android games, self-access centres, etc. Meanwhile, non-technical media are those teacher-made, non-mechanical aids, drawings, maps, etc.

Nowadays, IT-based teaching media are popular. Information and technology (IT) is created to enable, help, and process information [17][18]. The use of IT-based teaching media by considering characteristics of the lesson and students' needs is expected to boost students' enthusiasm to speak using *unggah-ungguh basa*. Teaching media can help students understand the materials easily. Students will not rely heavily on textbooks. Learning activities will not be monotonous because teaching media are various. IT-based teaching media can prevent students from being bored in the class. They offer several benefits. First, classroom interaction takes place. There are stimulus and responses that foster students' learning interest to speak. Second, they enable students to repeat teaching material that they have not understood yet. Third, learning media help students learn independently.

In this research, teacher-made media were given to students. The media are in the form of videos. The videos were self-produced by the teacher. In the videos, there are conversations which show the use of *unggah-ungguh basa* in various situations. The research question is whether the teacher-made media are effective to teach *unggah-ungguh basa* for high school students.

2. Method

In research design, pseudo experiment (quasi experimental design) was used. It is impossible to control all relevant variables. The research applied *Pretest-Posttest Control Group Design* where a group of people were taken from the population. They were given pretest and then consecutive treatments.

The scheme of *Pretest-Posttest Control Group Design* in this research was described as follows:

Table 1. Pretest-Posttest Control Group Design

Group	Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
Experimental	O ₁	X	O ₂
Control	O ₃	-	O ₄

Cluster Random Sampling was chosen. Each individual in the population has the same chance to be taken as sample members. The samples were the eleventh grade students of SMA N 7 Purworejo. The instruments in the research were observation and test. To analyze the data, there were two employed tests: normality test and homogeneity test. Hypotheses testing was then carried out to examine the differences in students' learning outcomes. The hypotheses testing using T-test was given in the pretest and posttest.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Data Description

There are 32 samples in control group did pretest and posttest. They were taught without using IT-based teaching media. The highest score in pretest was 87. The lowest score was 53. The range was 34. The mean score was 71.9. The standard deviation was 7.8. The variance was 62. The total score was 2.300. Meanwhile, the highest score in posttest was 87. The lowest score was 53. The range was 34. The mean score was 74.5. The standard deviation was 7.9. The variance was 62.44. The total score was 2.385.

Table 2. Pretest and posttest in control group

	N	Range	Min	Max	Sum	Mean Stat.	Std. error	Std. Deviation	Var.	Kurtosis Stat.	Std. error
Pre	32	34.00	53.00	87.00	2.300	71.87	1.39	7.8	62.11	.003	.809
Post	32	34.00	53.00	87.00	2.385	74.53	1.39	7.8	62.38	.704	.809
Valid N	32										

The 32 samples in experimental group did pretest and posttest. They were taught using teacher-made videos. The highest score in pretest was 80. The lowest score was 67. The range was 13. The mean score was 71.68. The standard deviation was 4.56. The variance was 18.9. The total score was 2.294. Meanwhile, the highest score in posttest was 90. The lowest score was 73. The range was 17. The mean score was 82.2. The standard deviation was 5.34. The variance was 28.5. The total score was 2.629.

Table 3. Pretest and posttest in experimental group

	N	Range	Min	Max	Sum	Mean Stat.	Std. error	Std. Deviation	Var.	Kurtosis Stat.	Std. error
Pre	32	13.00	67.00	80.00	2.294	71.68	.770	4.358	18.99	-.607	.809
Post	32	17.00	73.00	90.00	2.629	82.15	.944	5.340	28.52	-.927	.809
Valid N	32										

3.2 Hypotheses testing

In the hypotheses testing, there are three points tested: significance level, null hypothesis, and experimental significance test.

3.2.1 Significance level

Significance level is used to minimize false conclusion in the research. This is important to reject hypothesis to gain objective conclusion. Generally, significance level in the research is 5%. The significance level in this research is also 5%. This is to show that the falsity of the conclusion is 5% and the truth of the conclusion is 95%.

3.2.2 Null hypothesis

The hypothesis of the research (H_a) was the use of teacher-made media is effective to teach *unggah-ungguh basa* for high school students in Purworejo. To investigate whether the hypothesis was accepted or rejected, the hypothesis was turned into null hypothesis. The null hypothesis (H_0) was the use of teacher-made media are not effective to teach *unggah-ungguh basa* for high school students in Purworejo.

3.2.3 Experimental significance test

$$\begin{aligned}
 t &= \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)S_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)S_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2} \left[\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right]}} \\
 &= \frac{82,2 - 74,5}{\sqrt{\frac{(32-1)82,4 + (32-1)28,9}{62} \left[\frac{1}{32} + \frac{1}{32} \right]}} \\
 &= \frac{7,7}{\sqrt{\frac{(1984+896)(0,0625)}{62}}} \\
 &= \frac{7,7}{\sqrt{2,494}} \\
 &= \frac{7,7}{1,58} \\
 &= 4,87
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

With the significance level 5%, t_{table} is 2.000. The computation showed that t_{count} was higher than t_{table} ($4.87 > 2.000$). Thus, it could be concluded that the hypothesis of the research was accepted. H_a was accepted and H_0 was rejected. It means that the use of teacher-made media are effective to teach *unggah-ungguh basa* for high school students in Purworejo. It is also related to the context of the language leads to the context of the speech at that time which covers aspects of the identity of the participants, the time and place of the conversation, the topic of conversation, and the purpose of the conversation [19].

The use of teacher-made are effective to teach *unggah-ungguh* because in the Javanese, as a part of global society, have constantly had to deal with a variety of natural phenomena and have acceptability in technology advances [20]. The teacher-made designed to facilitate learning activity and information for student. It also more effective Interaction of teacher with students is multidirectional patterned on student centered learning [21]. This learning model supports the achievement of learning objectives that students can speak with the use of *basa krama* with *unggah ungguh*. Communication during teaching-learning process is needed as student's interaction with teacher is very important to realized a good quality learning

[22]. Therefore, the basic competencies and initial goals of learning can be realized using the right learning methods.

4. Conclusion

Technological advancement gives opportunities to teachers to shift the paradigm from conventional to IT-based learning. IT now has become an important aspect in all areas in lives including teaching-learning process. It can stimulate students' critical thinking. As a result, Javanese language teaching also requires technology. The finding of the research showed that the use of IT-based teaching media can yield better students' learning outcomes. This confirms that the use of technology in developing teaching media is important to support teaching quality and teaching process.

References

- [1] Rahman, A. and Ma, K., 2016, Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran IPS Berbasis Website untuk Siswa Kelas VII Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri, *J. Teknologi Pendidik*, **18(3)**, pp. 169–185.
- [2] Suwondo, T., 2014, “Ratusan Bahasa Daerah di Indonesia Punah”, *republika.co.id*, (4 March 2014).
- [3] Suwondo, T., 2014, “Bahasa Daerah Semakin Punah”, *republika.co.id*, (5 March 2014).
- [4] GF and CD F., 2018, *Ethnologue: Languages of the World*, ed. Simons, Texas: SIL International.
- [5] Sudaryanto, 1991, *Tata Bahasa Baku Bahasa Jawa*, Yogyakarta: Duta Wacana University Press.
- [6] Harjawiyana, S. H., 2001, *Kamus Unggah-Ungguh Basa Jawa*, Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- [7] Jackson, Nicholas, and Rahmat, 2013, Decoding Basa Walikan—A Preliminary Analysis of Yogyakarta ‘Reverse’ Language, *Int. J. of Indonesian Studies*, **1**, pp. 141-151.
- [8] Supartinah, 2006, Peran Pembelajaran Unggah-Ungguh Bahasa Jawa dalam Penanaman Nilai Sopan Santun di Sekolah Dasar”, *Jurnal Didaktika*, **1(1)**, p. 56.
- [9] Sasangka, S. S., 2009, *Unggah-Ungguh Basa Jawa*, Jakarta: Yayasan Paralingua.
- [10] Suseno, F. M., 2001, *Etika Jawa: Sebuah Analisa Falsafi Tentang Kebijakan Hidup Jawa*, Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- [11] De Sousa, Luiza, Richter, Barry and Nel, 2017, The Effect of Multimedia Use on the Teaching and Learning of Social Sciences at Tertiary Level: A case study, *Yesterday & Today*, **7**.
- [12] G. Sakkir, S. Dollah, and J. Ahmad, “Students’ Perceptions toward Using YouTube in EFL Classrooms ”, *J. Appl. Sci. Eng. Technol. Educ.*, **2** (1), pp. 1-10, 2020. doi:10.35877/454RI.asci2125.
- [13] Benson, Ambuko and Odera, F., 2013, Selection and Use of Media in Teaching Kiswahili Language in Secondary Schools in Kenya, *Int. J. of Information and Communication Technology Research*, **3** (1).
- [14] Rao, Bolla, and Mallikharjuna, 2014, Use of Media as an Instructional Tool in English Language Teaching (ELT) at Undergraduate Level, *Int. Journal of English and Literature*, **5** (6), pp. 141-143.
- [15] Naz, Ahsan, and Akbar, R. A., Use of Media for Effective Instruction Its Importance: Some Consideration, *Journal of Elementary Education*, **18** (1-2), pp. 35-40.
- [16] Hashemi, Masoud, and Azizinezhad, M., 2011, Teaching Media Translation: Which One to Choose, Technical or Non-Technical Media-Based Lessons?, *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, **28**, pp. 444-447.
- [17] Stair, G. R. R., 2011, *Fundamentals of Information System-Engage Learning*, Canada: Nelson Education.
- [18] A. F. Jafar, R. Rusli, M. Dinar, I. Irwan, and H. Hastuty, “The Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Flipped Classroom Learning Model Implementation in Integral Calculus”, *J. Appl. Sci. Eng.*

- Technol. Educ.*, **2(1)**, pp. 97-103, 2020. doi:10.35877/454RI.asci2144.
- [19] Saddhono, K., 2018, Cultural and social change of foreign students in Indonesia: The influence of Javanese Culture in Teaching Indonesian to Speakers of Other Languages (TISOL), In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* **126 (1)**, p. **012091**, IOP Publishing.
- [20] Widodo, S. T. and Saddhono, K., 2012, Petangan Tradition In Javanese Personal Naming Practice: An Ethnolinguistic Study, *Int Journal GEMA Online® Journal of Language Studies*, **12 (4)**, pp. **1165-1177**.
- [21] Sudikan, S. Y., 2017, Learning Model of Unggah-Ungguh Basa Oriented to Noble Behavior in SMP (Junior High School) Jawa Timur (East Java) Indonesia, *Int. Journal of Education and Practice*, **8 (9)**, pp. **169-177**.
- [22] Saddhono, K. and Rohmadi, M., 2014, A Sociolinguistics Study on the Use of the Javanese Language in the Learning Process in Primary Schools in Surakarta, Central Java, Indonesia, *Int. Journal International Education Studies*, **7 (6)**, pp. **25-30**.